

MANUFACTURING AND AGING OF TOUGH EPOXY COMPOSITE MATRICES

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INTRODUCTION

Tough epoxy polymers that don't crack are useful

Technology of toughening epoxy polymers is widespread

Rubber

Silica

Nano-carbon

Commercial drivers: **Reduce mould time, Manufacture faster**

Question 1:

Is a composite matrix resin cured at high speed as tough as one cured at low speed?

In-house formulation resin

In-house formulation hardener

Toughened with a polysiloxane core shell rubber (CSR) nanoparticle

Cured at different temperatures, hotter = faster cure

Addition of CSR nano-particles leads to a significant increase in toughness

Higher cure temperatures inhibit the toughenability of the epoxy polymer

Answer 1:

No

CONCLUSIONS

The toughness of rubber-toughened epoxies is **significantly adversely affected** by cure rate

Matrix formulations should be chosen by considering **speed of cure** as a commercial driver

Question 2:

Is a toughened composite as tough after aging as when it was manufactured?

Thermal aging reduces free volume

Fracture energy decreases with aging time

Thermal rejuvenation demonstrates recovery of fracture energy lost via thermal aging

Answer 2:

No

Physical aging **negatively** affects the toughness of rubber modified epoxy polymers

The effects of physical aging on toughened epoxy polymers are **recoverable**